

INDIVIDUAL POETIC FUNCTION OF SYNTACTIC REPETITION IN A POETIC TEXT (AS AN EXAMPLE OF KHURSHID DAVRON'S POETRY)

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Abstract: In the work of poem, the creator uses various similes and language elements to reveal his individual views. Studying the work of the poet Khurshid Davron, we can witness that together with the folk spirit, historicity occupies a leading place. The poet used many language elements to express his historical, social and national views. That is why its lexicon is rich and varied. The relationship between language and literature is also analyzed through his works. This article explains the elements of language, syntactic figures in Uzbek linguistics and their importance in literature. At the same time, while analyzing the connection between language and literature, the revelation of the human psyche with the help of language phenomena is studied.

Key words: Repetition, anaphore, epiphore, linguopoetics, stylistic figure

INTRODUCTION

The means of expression and image of the language, which serve to fulfill the methodological task in the language of literary literature, are also considered one of the most important signs that determine the position of the artistic style among other functional styles. Because although the need to use language tools in figurative, i.e. figurative, and in various forms for figurative images exists to a certain extent in all functional styles of language, but there is no opportunity to use them freely, freely, perfectly and in a wide range as in artistic style.

DISCUSSION

One of the most used stylistic tools in artistic speech and text is *repetition*. There are about thirty of them, for example, alliteration, anaphora, acromonogram (epanalipsis, epanaphora, anadiplosis), antistrophe, antanaclasis, antonomasia, antimetabola, metabola, refrain, monorhyme, pleonasm, rhyme, tautology, commentary, epiphora, epistrophe, epanode, epanasgrophe, circle. The existence of such types as acquisition, repetition, loop, and connection testifies to the wide range of possibilities of expression and image in the artistic style.

The linguist J. Lapasov defines repetition as follows: "The authors of the works of art use sounds and sounds, words and words in the works of art to draw the attention of the reader to the events described, and to exaggerate it. repeats sentences, increases emphasis, adds tension to the speech"[1.45].

In fact, any actions, similes, metaphors, image tools used by the writer and poet, in general, the creator, serve not to fill the text, but to enrich its content. It gives the work more artistic beauty, charm, pathos, upbeat spirit, and becomes an artistic tool of the thought that wants to be said. Repetitions do not always consist of words, for example they are phonetic

(of vowels or consonants) repetition, lexical (of words), syntactic repetition (of clauses, phrases or whole sentences)[2.55].

In the poetry of the poet Khurshid Davron, we can witness that syntactic repetition fulfills various stylistic tasks. For example, if we analyze the poem **“Ballad”**:

The battle ends slowly...

Black night... Black night...

Mother is silent. Around her

Black night... Black night...

Who knocks on the door?

Black night... Black night...

“It’s me, your son...”

The enemy is greedy!..

Black night... Black night...

Syntactic repetition of **“black night”** in the first stanza of the poem does not fulfill the same stylistic and semantic function as the rest of the stanzas. The “black nights” used to express the mental state of the hero boy and mother reveal a pragmatic meaning. In verse 1, “black night” means exactly – **one day**, “on one black and infamous night, the battle sura ended”, – says the creator. “Black night” in the second stanza means night and **darkness**. “Black night” in verse 3 corresponds to the meaning of **late hour**, while “black night” in verse 4 corresponds to the meaning of **this moment**.

“Is your brother a prisoner of war?”

Black night... Black night...

“Mom, forgive me!”

Black night... Black night...[3.156]

At the same time as syntactic repetition creates a poetic rhythm, each of them has a separate poetic function. As we have analyzed above, the syntactic repetition of “black night” in the sequence of these verses gives the meaning of **“my condition is ruined”** in the 5th verse, and in the 6th verse it reveals the purpose of guilt, **“my hand is short”** and I am weak.

RESULTS

The battle ends slowly... Black night... Black night...	one day
Mother is silent. Around her Black night... Black night...	darkness
Who knocks on the door? Black night... Black night...	late hour
“It’s me, your son...” The enemy is greedy!.. Black night... Black night...	this moment
“Is your brother a prisoner of war?” Black night... Black night...	my condition is ruined

“Mom, forgive me!” Black night... Black night...	my hand is short,
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CONCLUSION

So, in one place, repetition simply expresses gradualism, without performing any methodological task, in another place, repetition serves to increase effectiveness, and in another place, it expresses emphasis, emphasis on meaning. Sometimes, in his poems, the poet performs a satirical function of repetition, and sometimes he performs functions such as exaggeration, exaggeration, and strengthening. In general, the repetition and its types used in the poetry of Khurshid Davran is a tool that serves to strengthen the meaning, emphasize, generalize, confirm, contradict, express gradualness, impressiveness and melodiousness.

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